

A Deep Learning Based Digital Twin for Indoor Temperature Prediction in Smart Buildings

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Abstract—With the advent of the Internet of Things (IoT), smart buildings (SBs) are increasingly equipped with a variety of sensors, including those for temperature, humidity, lighting, and human presence. These SBs often incorporate automated heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems that generate substantial amounts of data daily. This data can be leveraged to develop and optimize energy-saving strategies. In this context, accurate indoor temperature prediction is essential for effective energy management. Moreover, if used properly, this prediction task can also improve the comfort within SBs. This paper proposes a novel approach to predicting indoor temperature called “Digital Twin for Temperature Prediction (DT4TP)” based on the digital twin paradigm and deep learning (DL) LSTM and BiLSTM models. DT4TP has been designed to process real-time and historical data from various IoT sensors in SBs during the winter and summer seasons and to predict the temperature in the future in such environments. DT4TP has been validated through a case study developed at ICAR-CNR in Rende, Italy, and through a state-of-the-art dataset collected from office rooms in Hebei, China. Furthermore, this paper compares the proposed approach with well-known algorithms such as ANN, DNN, CNN, LSTM, and GRU. The comparison uses metrics such as MAE, MSE, RMSE, and R^2 . The proposed approach can improve the temperature management of the HVAC system offering benefits for SB operations.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, Smart Building, Deep Learning, HVAC Control, Digital Twin, LSTM.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, various technologies support the development of smart cities and smart buildings (SBs) to meet the needs of officials, citizens, and businesses [1], [2]. Key among these technologies are the Internet of Things (IoT) [3] and Machine Learning (ML) [4], which foster the growth and well-being of smart environments. Energy consumption in SBs is a critical issue, as higher energy usage leads to increased greenhouse gas emissions, adversely impacting the environment and contributing to climate change. Consequently, effective energy-saving measures are essential to reduce carbon footprints and protect the planet [5].

The building sector is a major global energy consumer due to factors like population growth and improved building

infrastructure. HVAC systems in commercial and institutional buildings consume 59% of total energy, while globally, buildings use 30% of all energy [6]. Enhancing the energy efficiency of these systems is crucial to minimizing energy waste. ML and deep learning (DL) can significantly optimize HVAC systems in SBs, ensuring energy savings while maintaining comfort levels [7]. Predicting indoor temperatures allows SBs to preemptively manage HVAC operations, deciding when to switch them on or off and setting appropriate target temperatures.

Numerous studies have proposed ML [8]–[15] and DL [16]–[25] techniques for indoor temperature prediction to improve energy efficiency. However, there is a gap in using a digital twin (DT) approach for predicting indoor temperatures across different seasons. Also, existing studies often lack detailed data-processing steps, do not incorporate hyperparameter tuning for DL methods, and frequently omit validation using state-of-the-art datasets.

To address these gaps, this paper introduces a novel DL-based DT called “Digital Twin for Temperature Prediction (DT4TP)”, which integrates long short-term memory (LSTM) and bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) models to predict temperatures in SBs. DT4TP is designed for deployment in the edge-cloud continuum [26], although this paper does not specify the deployment details of its components. In this study, we collected data from real SBs and developed the DT4TP model to make accurate indoor temperature predictions, which will be used as input for a model predictive controller (MPC) for HVAC.

Regarding the technologies used, LSTM, a type of recurrent neural network, excels in remembering information over extended periods, making it ideal for tasks like prediction [27]. BiLSTM operates similarly but processes data bidirectionally, considering both past and future contexts [28]. DT involves creating a virtual model of a physical building, enhancing SBs by improving energy efficiency and occupant comfort through real-time monitoring, simulation, and energy optimization.

In summary, the key contributions of this work are:

- Proposing a novel DT approach based on LSTM and BiLSTM for indoor temperature prediction.
- Validating the proposed approach with real-time data from ICAR-CNR (Italy) and a state-of-the-art dataset from Hebei, China [29].

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- Comparing our results against well-known DL models (ANN, DNN, CNN, LSTM, and GRU), demonstrating superior performance in metrics like *MAE*, *MSE*, *RMSE*, and R^2 .

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews prior studies relevant to SBs and indoor temperature predictions. Section III describes the proposed approach in detail. Section IV presents the simulation test results. The final section concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we will examine recent work in the domain of SBs for predicting indoor temperature. While, in the early 2000s, statistical models like ARIMA were commonly used for indoor temperature prediction [8], recently, ML has been used to predict indoor temperatures in SBs. More in particular, popular ML algorithms such as Support Vector Regression (SVR) [9], Random Forest (RF) [10], and XGBoost [11] have been widely studied for temperature prediction. As examples, the works in [12]–[14] demonstrate the effectiveness of techniques such as RF and extra trees, especially to predict data related to time and the behavior of the HVAC system.

In the last few years, artificial neural networks (ANN) and DL have become popular due to their ability to handle interactions among non-linear features for indoor temperature predictions in SBs [15] [16]. In addition, for indoor temperature prediction, different studies [17]–[21] found that the ANN models provide an acceptable accuracy in predicting the indoor temperature.

Regarding DL models, the paper [23] utilized an LSTM model to predict the indoor temperature for 5 and 30 minutes in advance. The performance of the LSTM model was compared with other ML models, such as the backpropagation neural network, SVM, and decision tree. The results revealed that the LSTM model outperformed all other models. The GRU, a simplified version of LSTM, was used in the paper at [24], which proposed a hierarchical attention-GRU to predict indoor temperature. In addition, this work compares various ML/DL models with their proposed models. The paper in [25] presented an LSTM-based sequence-to-sequence model to predict multizone indoor temperature with improved performance over some existing advanced models, while the study in [23] utilized an error correction model to enhance the short-term indoor temperature prediction of an LSTM model.

Ensemble methods are also used in literature for indoor temperature prediction with good results. The study [22] explores an improved ensemble DL and ML framework, called DEML, to predict sensor-based indoor temperature in urban environments in Australia. In terms of prediction performance, DEML performed better than many benchmark models, including RF, SVM, gradient boosting, and LSTM.

A DT is a virtual version of a real-world object or system that is constantly updated with real-time data. It helps monitor, understand, and improve the real-world version by simulating its behavior digitally [30]. In the context of IoT or SBs, a DT can be seen as a virtual model of the building that uses

real-time data from sensors (like temperature, humidity, or occupancy) to monitor and control the building's environment. It helps improve efficiency, comfort, and energy use by simulating how changes in building systems would affect real-world performance [31].

In SBs, the DT has been used in various manners, but very few works, such as fault detection of HVAC systems [32], presented a novel DT framework to detect occupant discomfort [33] in SBs. The paper [34] introduces a data-driven method using wireless sensor networks and DT to improve the energy efficiency of the HVAC in SB. It used the LSTM model to predict indoor temperatures. The model was trained on sensor data from an SB for a potential MPC. Even if the work has some limitations, it is a first approach using the DT paradigm in buildings for temperature prediction.

To the best of our knowledge, the literature misses comprehensive approaches based on DT and DL for indoor temperature prediction that are designed for working in all seasons. Additionally, many studies do not validate the proposed approaches by using both real case studies and available state-of-the-art datasets from the literature.

To overcome this gap, this work proposes and validates DT4TP, namely Digital Twin for Temperature Prediction, which is an approach based on the digital twin paradigm and DL models that facilitates the prediction of the temperature indoor by using historical and actual sensor data.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

This section presents the proposed DT4TP approach, which includes an indoor temperature prediction model based on LSTM and BiLSTM architectures. The detailed structure of these models is discussed below. Figure 1 illustrates the basic architectures of such LSTM and BiLSTM models. In part A of the figure, the left side shows the LSTM model, highlighting the connections between LSTM cells, while the right side breaks down a single LSTM cell, showing its various gates (input, forget, and output). In part B, the diagram presents the BiLSTM model, which includes both the feedforward layer (FLR) and the feed backward layer (BLR), allowing it to process information in both directions. Detailed descriptions explaining each part of these models are provided below.

After obtaining and preprocessing data from multiple sensors, the sequential data is used as input in the LSTM layer. The LSTM layer and its workflow with various gates are explained in the following.

Forget gate (f_{gate}): The forget gate decides what information is eliminated from the cell state. The (f_{gate}) can be presented as:

$$f_{gate} = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f)$$

where, σ is the sigmoid function, W_f represents the weights of the features, b_f is the bias of the features, h_{t-1} is the previous output, and x_t is the current input of the features.

Input gate (i_{gate}) and Candidate layer (\tilde{C}_t): The (i_{gate}) and

(\tilde{C}_t) decide what new information about the features is to be added to the cell state. they can be presented as:

$$i_{tgate} = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C)$$

The i_{tgate} part decides which values will update the state, and \tilde{C}_t creates new candidate values that could be added to the state.

Output gate (o_{tgate}): In an LSTM, the output gate decides the information for the next hidden state. It checks the previous hidden state and the current input, and then determines which portion of the information should be passed on. The output gate filters the important information in the cell state and passes it to the hidden state, which is used in the next step. It is computed as:

$$o_{tgate} = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o)$$

$$h_t = o_{tgate} \times \tanh(C_t)$$

The hidden state h_t for the current time step is then computed by taking the element-wise product of the output gate (o_{tgate}) and the hyperbolic tangent of the cell state C_t .

The cell state is updated using these gates:

$$C_t = f_{tgate} \times C_{t-1} + i_{tgate} \times \tilde{C}_t$$

Here, the cell state C_t is modified by forgetting the old state $f_{tgate} \times C_{t-1}$ and adding new candidate values scaled by i_{tgate} .

After the LSTM model layer, we have also used BiLSTM one. The BiLSTM model layers process the input sequence in both forward and backward directions. The FLR of LSTM processes the input from start to end. It is computed as:

$$\vec{h}_t, \vec{C}_t = LSTM(\vec{h}_{t-1}, \vec{C}_{t-1}, x_t)$$

The BLR of LSTM processes the input from end to start. It is presented as:

$$\overleftarrow{h}_t, \overleftarrow{C}_t = LSTM(\overleftarrow{h}_{t+1}, \overleftarrow{C}_{t+1}, x_t)$$

For any given time step t , the outputs from the forward and backward LSTMs are typically combined (e.g., concatenated or summed) to get the final output presented as:

$$h_t = [\vec{h}_t; \overleftarrow{h}_t]$$

or

$$h_t = \vec{h}_t + \overleftarrow{h}_t$$

As BiLSTMs can process data from both the past and the future, they can provide better understanding of input sequences. An additional LSTM layer is included in the proposed architecture to improve temperature prediction. The final LSTM output (h_t) is passed to a dense layer which outputs the predicted indoor temperature. This layer simply performs a linear transformation presented as:

$$Predicted_{temperature} = W_{de} \cdot h_t + b_{de}$$

Fig. 1: LSTM and BiLSTM Architecture

where W_{de} and b_{de} are the weights and bias of the dense layer, respectively.

The model development architecture is detailed in Section IV.

IV. A CASE STUDY FOR DT4TP

This section focuses on the validation of DT4TP through a case study developed at the ICAR-CNR headquarters in the IoT Laboratory, Italy, for predicting indoor temperatures during summer and winter seasons. The laboratory at ICAR-CNR has deployed a system with sensors and actuators of different technologies and Raspberry Pi as edge/cloud computing nodes for collecting and processing data [35]. The developed DT has been executed for this case study on an Intel Core i7-7567U PC with 16 GB of RAM. It has been implemented in Python language by also using several libraries for data preprocessing and building models, such as *Pandas 2.03*, *Numpy 1.5.0*, *Matplotlib 3.7.2*, *Scikit-learn 1.3.0*, *TensorFlow* and *Keras 2.15.0*.

For this case study, we used various data such as the ones coming from Indoor Temperature/Humidity, Outdoor Temperature, IR Occupancy, Light, HVAC status (giving HVAC setpoint, power, fan speed), and air quality monitor (AQM) sensors. Data was collected during working hours with different timescales, so to create two datasets for the months of October 2023 and June 2024, corresponding to the summer and winter seasons in Italy. The raw data was saved in CSV files, and then it was loaded into a *Pandas DataFrame*. The "Time" column was converted into a *Pandas DateTime* object for time-based operations. Data from Saturdays and Sundays was excluded since workdays are Monday-Friday. To prepare the collected data for the prediction tasks in this case study, it was resampled to create two datasets for winter and two for summer, with 3-minute and 8-minute granularity, respectively. Missing values were filled using backward filling. In this paper, two types of features were identified, namely categorical (i.e., occupancy, HVAC fan speed, and status) and

numerical (such as humidity, lighting, indoor temperature, and air quality).

Figure 2.A, shows the detailed data collection and pre-processing steps, including converting Unix time to readable time, data type conversion, handling *null/Nan* values, *backward/forward* fill, etc. The *numerical data* was normalized using *MinMaxScaler* to scale the features to a range between 0 and 1. This normalization helps speed up the learning process and improve model performance by treating all features equally. *Categorical* variables were transformed using *OneHotEncoder*, which converts each categorical value into a new categorical column and assigns a 1 or 0 (*True/False*). This process is essential for handling non-numeric data in DL models. To prepare the data for the DT4TP models, sequences of data points were created. Each sequence consists of data from a fixed number of time steps before the target time, allowing the model to learn from historical data to predict future conditions. Finally, the data set was divided into training (80%), validation (20% of the training set), and test (20%) sets. This separation allows for the training of the model on one subset of data and the evaluation of its performance on an independent set of data, ensuring that the model generalizes well to new, unseen data (test data).

The DT4TP allows for hyperparameter tuning across various parameters, including epochs, layers, neurons, batch size, and dropout. Anyway, the details on the tuning of these parameters will be detailed in our future works. For this work, we identified the optimal parameters that enhanced accuracy for metrics such as *MAE*, *MSE*, *RMSE*, and R^2 .

A. DT4TP Architecture for the considered Case Study

DT4TP has been designed so to merge several models, which are organized as layers. The first one consists of an LSTM layer with 128 units chosen for the highest accuracy and efficiency. This unit processes the input sequence and returns the full sequence of outputs for the next layer. This layer sets `return_sequences=True`, which means that it will return output for every time step in the input sequence, not just the final output. This allows the next layer in our model to have access to the entire sequence of outputs, providing a richer set of data to learn from. Additionally, we have a dropout layer right after the LSTM layer. The dropout layer helps prevent overfitting by randomly turning off 20% of the neurons during training, making the DT4TP approach more robust and better at generalizing to new data.

After the first LSTM layer, DT4TP comprehends a BiLSTM layer with 64 units, which processes the data in both forward and backward directions, and also keeps the output from every step. Just like in the previous LSTM layer, the `return_sequences=True` parameter ensures that outputs for all time steps are returned. This provides detailed information to the subsequent layers, allowing them to have a comprehensive understanding of the entire sequence. Following the BiLSTM layer, we have another dropout layer, which again helps in preventing overfitting.

After the BiLSTM one, DT4TP includes another LSTM layer with 64 units that uses `return_sequences=False`, which means that it will only return the final output. Another dropout layer is applied here as well. Finally, a dense layer with a single unit is added, which produces the final output of DT4TP for indoor temperature prediction. It uses a linear activation function. The purpose of this last layer is to refine the features extracted by the previous layers in preparation for the final output prediction. In addition, the proposed approach also used the Adam optimizer. It has been chosen for its efficiency in handling sparse gradients and adaptive learning rate capabilities.

In summary, the LSTM and BiLSTM cells are utilized in both directions, which significantly enhances the model's ability to capture complex data patterns. The global architecture of DT4TP described above, with all its layers, is shown in figure 2.B.

B. Result analysis and discussion

In this subsection, the paper will discuss the results of the proposed DT4TP on the data collected at the ICAR-CNR IoT Lab. Moreover, we will validate DT4TP using another state-of-the-art dataset from the literature. For the evaluation, we will consider metrics such as *MAE*, *MSE*, *RMSE*, and R^2 .

DT4TP has been trained and tested with good results for different epoch numbers (i.e., 10, 30, 50, 80, and 100). However, in the rest of the paper and due to lack of space, we'll show only the results obtained by considering 30 epochs.

Figure 3 (left part) shows the training and validation losses of DT4TP, which are very close to each other. Additionally, the right side of the figure displays the actual and predicted indoor temperatures in the test dataset of June 2024. It was a 3-minute interval prediction, where the actual and predicted temperature graphs were very close. These two graphs demonstrate that the DT4TP proposed model fits this dataset very well.

Table I shows the metrics mentioned above calculated on DT4TP's predictions at three minutes and eight minutes in the future. Moreover, in the table, a comparison with state-of-the-art algorithms is shown. The table distinguishes between summer and winter data. For the three-minute predictions in October, the proposed model achieved for *MAE*: 0.01007, *MSE*: 0.000365, *RMSE*: 0.019109, and R^2 : 0.981928. For the eight-minute predictions, the proposed model achieved for *MAE*: 0.010975, *MSE*: 0.000645, *RMSE*: 0.025399, R^2 : 0.964930. Similarly, the results of the data gathered in June are also highlighted in the table. It is worth noting that the proposed model performs better than the other algorithms in most metrics.

a) Performance of DT4TP in state-of-the-art datasets:

We applied the proposed approach to public available data to further evaluate its performance, accuracy, effectiveness, and reliability. Below, we describe one dataset and how our proposed approach worked on it.

We used a state-of-the-art dataset that was collected from 6 office room environments in Hebei, China [29]. Data were collected from a variety of multisensor sources

Fig. 2: The workflow realized for the case study by using DT4TP.

Fig. 3: Training and validation loss of DT4TP (left) and actual vs predicted temperatures in the testing dataset of DT4TP (right) - June 2024 dataset.

TABLE I: Validation of DT4TP for temperature prediction (3 and 8 minutes ahead) using winter and summer data from the IoT Lab, ICAR-CNR, Italy.

	3 Minutes					8 Minutes			
	Models	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ²	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ²
June	FFNN	0.041455	0.002804	0.052959	0.901874	0.029610	0.001692	0.041135	0.941979
	ANN	0.044621	0.004312	0.064641	0.849121	0.052519	0.005047	0.071043	0.826941
	DNN	0.039682	0.002995	0.054732	0.895196	0.036756	0.002625	0.051243	0.909962
	CNN	0.006195	0.000113	0.010659	0.996024	0.013530	0.000536	0.023170	0.981592
	RNN	0.009032	0.000151	0.012312	0.994696	0.012990	0.000489	0.022130	0.983207
	LSTM	0.004411	0.000041	0.006478	0.998531	0.013826	0.000426	0.020640	0.985392
	GRU	0.004416	0.0000427	0.006542	0.998502	0.014007	0.000432	0.020926	0.984984
	Proposed	0.004522	0.000037	0.006098	0.998698	0.010188	0.000305	0.017481	0.989521
October	FFNN	0.021741	0.001566	0.039585	0.922455	0.021440	0.001546	0.039326	0.915925
	ANN	0.038826	0.004200	0.064808	0.792147	0.034457	0.003807	0.061705	0.793013
	DNN	0.030800	0.002823	0.053137	0.860268	0.034457	0.003807	0.061705	0.793013
	CNN	0.007439	0.000364	0.019123	0.981902	0.010731	0.000741	0.027224	0.959709
	RNN	0.018677	0.000842	0.029028	0.958301	0.012940	0.000794	0.028190	0.956797
	LSTM	0.010211	0.000419	0.020469	0.979264	0.009636	0.000670	0.025899	0.963533
	GRU	0.021011	0.000658	0.025654	0.967431	0.008976	0.000698	0.026432	0.962019
	Proposed	0.010075	0.000365	0.019109	0.981928	0.010975	0.000645	0.025399	0.964930

TABLE II: Validation of DT4TP on the state-of-the-art dataset collected in Hebei, China [29].

Model	Room 1				Room 2			
	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ²	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ²
FFNN	0.042111	0.003565	0.059710	0.865390	0.087092	0.011198	0.105821	0.752275
ANN	0.052959	0.004497	0.067062	0.830197	0.080836	0.009067	0.095225	0.799399
DNN	0.109462	0.014696	0.121229	0.445124	0.122584	0.018920	0.137553	0.581431
CNN	0.020496	0.001146	0.033864	0.956701	0.057922	0.007788	0.088250	0.827710
RNN	0.077125	0.006991	0.083616	0.736026	0.033721	0.002429	0.049285	0.946265
LSTM	0.024135	0.001121	0.033490	0.957652	0.026445	0.001432	0.037847	0.968311
GRU	0.024621	0.001482	0.038509	0.944009	0.024542	0.001325	0.036409	0.970674
Proposed (3)	0.018781	0.000950	0.030834	0.964103	0.018565	0.000960	0.030988	0.978756

(e.g., indoor/outdoor temperatures, humidity, FCU fan, multi-occupancy, outdoor features and etc). The data was collected during the summer period in August 2021, when the HVAC was working.

Given the dataset so far described, after preprocessing the data, we applied the DT4TP approach. Table II shows the results we gathered for the chosen evaluation metrics in the selected rooms. More in particular, we display the results for the predictions in 3 minutes in the future.

Based on various metrics (*MAE*, *MSE*, *RMSE*, and R^2), we can conclude that our approach performs well in different environments. When applied to the public state-of-the-art dataset from Hebei, we obtained good results for both the considered rooms.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper had introduced a novel approach, called DT4TP, for predicting indoor temperatures in SBs using the digital twin paradigm combined with DL models, such as LSTM and BiLSTM. By leveraging real-time and historical data from IoT sensors, DT4TP can enhance the management of HVAC systems, leading to significant energy savings and improved comfort.

Our approach has been validated through a case study at ICAR-CNR in Italy and a state-of-the-art dataset from Hebei, China. The results have shown that DT4TP not only accurately predicts indoor temperatures but also outperforms well-known models such as ANN, DNN, CNN, LSTM, and GRU in metrics like MAE, MSE, RMSE, and R^2 . These findings confirm that DT4TP is both accurate and reliable across different datasets, which is essential for real-world applications where the model must perform under diverse conditions.

In future work, we aim to extend DT4TP to recognize and predict not only indoor temperature but also specific activities within the building. Furthermore, we plan to enhance our case study by including additional rooms in our research institute and applying data augmentation or transfer learning techniques to address data scarcity.

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